

SCIENTIFIC THEORY OF DEVELOPING TEACHERS' DIGITAL SKILLS OF THE SECONDARY EDUCATION SYSTEM

Sherzod Karimov Farxotovich

Institute for Retraining and Professional Development of Higher Education Personnel, Tashkent

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10511162>

Abstract. *You will be able to familiarize yourself with the analysis of technologies that develop the skills of teachers of general secondary education aimed at learning in a digital educational environment, and the content of using these technologies in the educational process. It is also possible to track information about the stages of the qualitative organization of the educational process according to these developing technologies.*

Keywords: *digital education, digital skills, developmental technology, teaching staff.*

Introduction: General secondary education requires the implementation of the educational process based on the skills of teachers in the digital educational environment in the system of continuous professional development with the help of technologies for the development of digital skills of pedagogues. At the same time, the teaching staff is focused on technologies and methods that develop digital skills for the distance learning environment.

The object of the study: Distance learning environment of general secondary education of pedagogic personnel.

Practical process methods: By studying and analyzing the existing skills of pedagogic personnel in the form of traditional education, it will be possible to use various methods for the organization and management of educational processes in the general secondary education system by teaching staff. Follow these: **Analysis of educational literature in the field:** There will be an opportunity to study existing foreign literature related to the field, scientific dissertations, articles, scientific-practical conference collections, monographs written by experts and specialists.

Questionnaire: Various questionnaires can be conducted in order to study the digital skills of general secondary education pedagogues. With the help of such online questionnaires, it is ensured that the selected dissertation will have the necessary analytical information.

Conversations: Organizing online conversations with representatives of higher education institutions, advanced scientists, experts, creating social groups among social network users and conducting online communication, expressing opinions related to the topic online using various forums and chats, real-time webinar, o It is possible to communicate face-to-face with representatives of the field and exchange ideas in seminars, master-classes and trainings.

Observations: General secondary education pedagogic personnel, along with education and training of today's students, in the system of continuous professional development, with continuous professional development within their subject, the possibilities of digital education technology in the educational process, the application of its methodology it will be possible to study and analyze practical processes such as At the same time, it will be possible to see the answers to a number of questions about whether each teacher in the educational system has the skills and qualifications to use modern technologies in the development of pedagogical skills during the observations. **Case Studies:** In the course of the general secondary education system,

the study of the cases of the use of technologies aimed at developing the skills of the teacher in the digital educational environment by the teaching staff, the extent to which the technologies aimed at the development of digital skills and competence are used in the system of continuous professional development analysis of situations, methods that develop digital skills, an opportunity to effectively study the conditions intended to determine the effectiveness of the organization of educational activities will appear. **Analyzing digital skills:** In the analysis of the digital skills of general secondary education pedagogic personnel, analyzes conducted by experts, specialists, scientists of foreign countries in this field, as well as scientific articles and scientific-practical conference collection materials, theoretical material and educational literature analysis, study of theoretical information on the need for skills of pedagogues for the digital educational environment, and methods that develop the digital skills of the teaching staff in the general secondary education sector of education and provides the ability to analyze practical processes through technologies.

Integration of developing technologies among general secondary education pedagogic personnel: The following technologies are included in the development of digital skills of general secondary education pedagogic personnel:

Technologies that develop digital skills	
Online course and Educational programs	There are many educational programs and distance learning, online courses that develop the pedagogical skills of school teachers, free and paid courses are provided. These online courses are conducted by professors, teachers and specialists of various educational organizations.
Webinar	Webinar sessions are organized in real time, and listeners can interact within the topic and ask questions to the teacher. In the webinars, it will be possible to provide information to the webinar participants about the features and other aspects of the possibilities of digital technology, and it will be possible to conduct online lectures by the professor and teaching team of the educational institution.
E-learning resources and platforms	Many electronic platforms, digital educational tools and resources will be developed and presented by public and private sector officials for the use of pedagogues in the educational process, and at the same time for them to acquire digital skills.
Sharing experience	It is the most convenient and effective way to develop digital skills. During the educational process, teaching staff will be provided with opportunities to share their knowledge and skills in the use of digital technologies and to exchange ideas.
Consultation	Pedagogical personnel are provided with advice, recommendations and instructions on how to use digital educational tools and electronic educational platforms.

1-figure. Development of digital skills of teaching stafftechnologies

In the educational process, several stages are covered in improving the quality of education using technologies that develop the highly recorded digital skills of pedagogues:

Diagnostics of digital skills of teaching staff– at this stage, the teacher conducts learning by analyzing the diagnostic parameters of employees, that is, digital skills for the educational process. In this case, it will be possible to determine the possibilities of cloud technology, using a questionnaire and test questions using software tools.

Formation of programs for the development of digital skills – By developing a program based on the diagnosis of pedagogical personnel, the main attention should be paid to the needs of secondary school teachers and their level of professional training in this program.

Implementation of digital skills development program – in the implementation of this digital skills development program, it will be possible to use various methods and technologies, such as webinars, educational training, master classes.

Evaluation and monitoring results of the development of digital skills – at this stage, the results of evaluation and monitoring of digital skills of pedagogues are carried out. It serves to determine to what extent the digital skills development program has been developed and which areas of this program should be further developed.

Rating and feedback: determining the level of ICT literacy in the conditions of the digital educational environment while monitoring the development of digital skills of teaching staff, as well as teaching information security using technology opportunities that develop the digital skills of the teacher in the electronic information educational environment also helps to ride.

Continuous provision of digital learning resources: digital educational resources for continuous development of digital skills of pedagogues of general secondary education, constantly updated online courses on electronic educational platforms, the latest advanced modern technologies for improving the quality of digital education in the educational process requires continuous provision of application methods, methodologies and approaches.

Formation of digital literacy: in the educational process, in order to integrate the digital literacy of pedagogues into educational standards and curricula, first of all, it requires the development of effective strategies that shape digital literacy by defining educational goals, and software tools and technologies. It will be possible to observe to what extent digital literacy is formed in the digital educational environment based on the effective teaching approaches of using these tools and technologies by the teacher for the educational process.

In conclusion, it is evident in the educational process that the development of digital skills of pedagogues is one of the urgent tasks, as it becomes a necessity to use the opportunities of digital technology. In this process, using the capabilities of the modern digital educational platform, the demand of the teacher to form digital competence, skills and literacy has become the main task of the digital educational environment.

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